

TIME AND IT'S SIGNIFICANCE IN OUR LIFETIME.

Nargiza Aliyeva Ravshanjon qizi,
1st year master's student,
Namangan State Pedagogical Institute.

***Abstract.** Time. Time is the abstract concept that passes very fast and very valuable wealth for someone who cares about it, and nothing for people who do not value it. Each personality has the same time to live in mostly in a day, but we see that many differences in people's achievements. Successful people always try to save their time, manage it correctly, and use even seconds for their own progress, and this is the key of their success from many decades. In this paper, I try to discuss about the value of time, its significance in our life. Furthermore, quotes and life stories from famous and successful people and the distractions from the technologies in our century.*

***Keywords;** time management, significance, strategies.*

I. Introduction.

Time is the existence and event in the past, present, and future taken as a whole will continue to advance indefinitely [1]. Time is the abstract concept that we cannot change or improve it. We can only use it wisely and maximally. Time management is used in many speeches, resources, and other information, but time cannot be managed as it is an inaccessible concept for all of us. Each personality has 24 hours in a day; how to use it and deal with it in their work. While saying time management, we endeavour to express the ways, strategies to use our time successfully and do not remove time-consuming and useless actions of our time. There are several well-known methods to effectively use the time, but according to [2] definition and theories in the field of time management is not enough to utilize. In his review of 32 empirical researches in this topic until the 2005.

Furthermore, Uzbekistan and its history has a great personalities, who are famous for their attention in the educational and well-known ancestors, their actions, and stories, to save their time and famous and useful quotes are given to remind the significance of time in our life.

Additionally, the role of technologies and social media in our time usage is discussed widely, as it has many distractions and time-consuming content on social networks such as Instagram, Telegram, Facebook and so on. In this article, I will discuss above mentioned issues and review of articles in related topic to provide information about time management.

II. Literature review.

Hour, o'clock or time these are the same notions that are described differently by a great many of scientists and dictionaries. Time is studied in various directions and time can be described in mathematics as a continual and continuous series of events that take place one after another, from the past through the today, and into the future.[3] Time is defined by physicists as the flow of the past events through the present and into the future. In essence, a system is timeless if it is unchanging. When describing events that take place in three-dimensional space, time can be thought of as the 4th dimension of reality. We cannot see, feel, or taste it, so we can measure the passage of time.[4] Merriam Webster dictionary describes time as the period that something happens, goes through a process, or stays the same. [5] Time is an illusion, says theoretical physicist Carlo Rovelli, because our simple notion of its flow doesn't match up with actual reality. In fact, much more, including Isaac Newton's depiction of a constantly ticking clock, is illusory, according to Rovelli's claim in *The Order of Time*. Even relativistic space-time, which Albert Einstein described as an elastic manifold that bends depending on a person's relative speed or closeness to a mass, is only a useful simplification.[6]

Time is unstoppable as the humanity does not know to stop or even touch it due to its abstractness, time is irreversible so past actions cannot be changed and today's

our activities become irreversibly. In order to occur anything in this world we need time which is required and time is measured as an 24 hours, a week, a year etc ...

Time is absolute according to Isaac Newton' theory and relative time is explored by Albert Einstein, additionally time can be subjective with the sequence of feeling of human being, if you are happy time pass quickly and it slows down when you feeling is changed.[7]

Many humanity waste their time and regret about it that they have wasted not only time but the successful and profitable work, study or lifetime where they could do their best to obtain something. For each of us given 24 hours, 1440 minutes and 86400 seconds to utilize, live in and work however people live different years but if you are more than 60 years old that you are got everything in this life. Now, The importance of being punctual is explained, If an average life of seventy-five years is analyzed, what is the main time spent on?

1. The time around 15 years is childhood and adolescence wins with;
2. In the last sixty years, eight a day if he sleeps after the clock, he will spend 20 years of his life with sleep;
3. If you work hard for eight hours a day, it means twenty years of work ;
4. If three meals are served in one day, for each meal is spend half an hour, it takes three years and eighteen the month of life goes to courtship;
5. The last six years of life are worship, family and so on.

A man's life is spent on his activities, mostly that we do not understand or pay attention. We continue with the quotes from famous personalities and their life plans and achievements as their achievements demonstrate how they value their time. It would be preferable to list 3 people who are on the most famous and successful personalities list and find out what they do to and what they are doing in their time today.

Elon Musk is the well-known person and his daily routine is interesting for each of us. He mostly sleeps 6 to 6,5 hours in a day, most of his time is spend on his projects

and work as he is the founder of the companies SpaceX and Tesla according to his schedule he works 42 hours in Tesla and 40 hours in his SpaceX company per week and as he is so busy he doesn't pay attention for his nutrition and eating. He admits that his success is layed on his effrot and time management technique that he has called " time boxing or timeblocking" [8]

"Avoid making the same choice twice. Spend some time and consideration to decide wisely the first time so that you don't needlessly revisit the matter. Reopening arguments too frequently interferes not only with your ability to carry out your plan but also with your desire to make a choice in the first place. After all, why decide something if it's not really decided? – Mr. Bill Gates.[9] Bill Gates also spend his time on his work more and according to that he is outstanding person.

Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf, may God bless him and grant him peace, is an accomplished scholar, commentator, muhaddith, jurist, murshid, a great representative of the Islamic world of his time, a great figure, a people's deputy of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR, a former mufti of the Religious Office of the Muslims of Central Asia and Kazakhstan, an independent He was the first mufti of Uzbekistan, a member of many international scientific institutions, religious organizations, and the religious leader of the people of Movarounnahr. In his life between 1952-2015 years he loved and did many prosperous works. During this time he has written more than 50 books [10]which are read by the learners today. Our Sheikh not only wrote but he was an active in social life, studied and worked each day. As you see , these people managed to do these much works and fortunate in their life due to their best time management skills and they value each their minutes. 21st century is the century of technologies. Everyone has their gadgets telephones pr laptop, compiter and so on on their hands today. But nowadays there are many leisure time activities games that are eating oir time and losing our time by sitting on this sites by hours. Social networks such as Instagram Telegram Facebook Twitter are the networks that you may spend your whole day by sitting and watching

different content videos even if you need or not you will just lose your time there which is a great regret. The average amount of time spent online throughout the nine quarters from Q2 2020 to Q2 2022 was 417 minutes (six hours and 57 minutes) every day, peaking in Q2 2021 and Q3 2021. In 2021, internet users worldwide logged on for 415.5 minutes per day on average. The current 2022 average is 403 minutes, which is 12.5 minutes shorter. [11] Almost 7 hours a day is spend on the network, on the Internet and this means almost 1/3 of our life, as we sleep 1/3 another 1 part 8 hours for internet and 8 hours is left for work, study, family, sport and every activity that human does in his lifetime.

III. Conclusion.

To sum up, time is the most valuable concept that humanity has, by utilizing time they can achieve the highest results in this life. One of the celebreted Islam scholars Khasan Basriy said – “you are consisted of days, if one day of yours is wasted, your part is lost”, by these works he endeavours us to use our munites, even seconds to make good to people and learn new knowledge and do not waste our time. As we saw in this article, prominent people of our century as Sheyikh Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf , Elon Mask, and Bill Gates in the list of as well-known and successful people managed to do many works and continuing this by using their time maxcimally. Although, technologies, computer games, the internet, social media are attractive and most time consuming places where our youth is wasting their time and valuable life there. All of us must try to make good and use our time for valuable and usefull thing in this world.

IV. References.

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